

Preventing Collision Avoidance Deadlocks in Multiagent Navigation for Deterministic Simulation

Stéphane Gros-Lemesre
Crytek GmbH
Frankfurt am Main, Germany
s.groslemesre@gmail.com

Abstract—The **Optimal Reciprocal Collision Avoidance (ORCA)** algorithm is a foundational method for decentralized multiagent navigation, particularly valued for its lightweight implementation and robustness in crowded contexts. Originally developed for robotics, environmental noise and motion uncertainty are inherent, ORCA has become a standard in video game Artificial Intelligence (AI). However, in highly deterministic environments characterized by small integration time steps, which typically arise in modern asynchronous game simulations, the absence of stochasticity leads to systemic deadlocks in symmetric configurations that do not occur in noisy real-world systems. By analyzing the construction of the half-plane velocity constraints in ORCA, we identify the geometric origin of these deadlocks. We demonstrate that deadlocks occur systematically across all symmetric scenarios for $n \in [2, 30]$ agents when exact rotational symmetry is preserved, especially with small time steps or slow agents. We present Revised ORCA Logic (RORCAL), a lightweight post-processing mechanism that introduces minimal directional bias to resolve degenerate solutions while preserving ORCA’s computational efficiency. Experimental results show that RORCAL resolves all tested deadlock scenarios with a 2% per-iteration overhead and achieves 23% faster resolution in a 250-agents benchmark through emergent rotational coordination.

Index Terms—multiagent navigation, collision avoidance, ORCA, deadlock, game AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiagent collision avoidance is essential to robotics, crowd simulation, and game Artificial Intelligence (AI). Optimal Reciprocal Collision Avoidance (ORCA) [1] has become widely adopted across multiple fields. ORCA constructs velocity constraints as half-planes in velocity space (VS) and selects new agent velocities through linear programming, providing sufficient conditions for collision-free motion with $O(n)$ complexity per agent.

Despite its widespread use, ORCA exhibits systemic deadlocks in symmetric configurations. When agents approach from opposite directions or converge toward a common point, ORCA’s velocity selection can produce degenerate solutions that reduce speed without lateral deviation, leading to monotonic convergence to zero velocity (deadlock). These deadlocks are particularly problematic in game contexts, where deterministic simulation and symmetric spawning scenarios occur naturally.

Existing approaches to ORCA deadlocks include hybrid methods combining ORCA with Multiagent Path Finding [2], [3], perturbation schemes [4], [5], and velocity constraint modifications [10]. However, the fundamental geometric causes

of these deadlocks have not been systematically analyzed, and lightweight preventive solutions for deterministic game simulations remain unexplored.

This paper makes three contributions. First, we provide a geometric analysis identifying specific configurations where ORCA produces degenerate velocity solutions: perpendicular ORCA constraints in two-agent scenarios and reflex constraint wedges in multiagent scenarios. Second, we demonstrate that these deadlocks occur systematically across all symmetric configurations for $n \in [2, 30]$ agents when exact symmetry is preserved and are more likely to happen with small time steps or slow agents. Third, we present Revised ORCA Logic (RORCAL), a lightweight correction mechanism that introduces minimal directional bias to break symmetric deadlocks whilst preserving ORCA’s efficiency and decentralized operation.

Experimental validation shows RORCAL resolves all tested symmetric deadlock scenarios with minimal computational overhead (2% per iteration). In the $n = 250$ benchmark scenario, RORCAL achieves 23% faster resolution through emergent rotational coordination. The approach is practical for game development, providing deterministic deadlock resolution without relying on numerical noise or randomization.

II. BACKGROUND

Multiagent collision avoidance has been extensively studied in robotics, crowd simulation, and game AI. In this section we review the foundational velocity obstacle (VO) approaches and discuss known limitations of ORCA.

A. Velocity Obstacles

Fiorini and Shiller [6] introduced the concept of *velocity obstacles* for robot motion planning in dynamic environments. The VO represents the set of robot velocities that would result in a collision with a moving obstacle at some future time. By selecting velocities outside this forbidden region in VS, an agent can avoid collisions in a first-order reactive manner.

The VO approach is the foundation for many decentralized collision avoidance algorithms. However, when applied to multiagent scenarios where all agents use VOs, oscillations occur as agents repeatedly predict non-reactive obstacle motion and adjust accordingly [7].

B. Reciprocal Velocity Obstacles and ORCA

Van den Berg et al. [7] addressed the oscillation problem with Reciprocal Velocity Obstacles (RVO), where each agent

assumes the other will also perform collision avoidance and takes half the responsibility for the maneuver. This reciprocal assumption enables smoother multiagent navigation.

Building on RVO, van den Berg et al. [1] formulated ORCA. ORCA provides sufficient conditions for collision-free motion by constructing half-planes of permitted velocities in VS. For each neighboring agent, ORCA computes a half-plane constraint based on the VO geometry. The agent then selects its new velocity by solving a low-dimensional linear program (LP) that finds the permitted velocity closest to its preferred velocity (\mathbf{v}^{pref}).

ORCA's key advantages include computational efficiency (linear programming with $O(n)$ constraints), decentralized operation (no communication), and smooth motion in typical scenarios. The algorithm is widely adopted in games [8], crowd simulation, and robotic systems, with implementations like the RVO2 library [9] seeing extensive use.

C. Known Limitations

Despite its widespread adoption, ORCA has recognized limitations. Sunshine-Hill [8] provides a detailed analysis of how ORCA behaves in practice, noting that the guarantee of collision-free motion only holds under specific conditions and that three-agent scenarios can lead to inconsistent passing intentions.

Several extensions address specific issues: Constant Speed ORCA (CSORCA) [10] improves performance for speed-constrained aircraft, while V-RVO [11] uses Voronoi diagrams to reduce conservativeness. Researchers have also identified that ORCA is prone to deadlocks in constrained environments [2], [3], [5], leading to hybrid approaches that combine ORCA with Multiagent Path Finding (MAPF) algorithms like Push and Rotate [2] or Enhanced Conflict-Based Search (ECBS) [3] to resolve deadlock situations when detected.

Recent works have focused on deadlock detection and resolution. Strategic approaches use pseudo-goal perturbation [4] or control barrier functions [5] to escape deadlocks once detected. However, these methods are reactive rather than preventive, and the fundamental geometric causes of deadlock in ORCA remain under-explored in the literature.

D. Alternative Approaches

For completeness, we note that other multiagent navigation paradigms exist. The Social Force Model [12], [13] treats pedestrians as particles subject to social forces, achieving realistic crowd behavior, but without formal collision avoidance guarantees. Learning-based approaches have also emerged, yet they often incorporate VO geometry as part of the observation space [14].

Our work focuses specifically on understanding and resolving geometric failure modes intrinsic to ORCA's formulation, providing a principled solution that maintains ORCA's computational efficiency and decentralized nature.

III. GEOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF DEADLOCKS

In this section, we identify and analyze fundamental geometric configurations in which ORCA produces degenerate

velocity solutions that lead to deadlock, especially with the optimization velocity defined as recommended in the original paper as $\mathbf{v}_A^{\text{opt}} = \mathbf{v}_A$ [1]. We demonstrate that when agents are in symmetric configurations these failure modes arise from the geometric construction of ORCA half-planes.

A. Two-Agent Head-On Collision

1) *Configuration*: Consider two agents A and B with radius r_A and r_B and maximum speed v_A^{max} and v_B^{max} respectively, positioned symmetrically with respect to their goal positions. Agent A is located at position $\mathbf{p}_A = (-d, 0)$ with goal g_A at $(d, 0)$, while agent B is at $\mathbf{p}_B = (d, 0)$ with goal g_B at $(-d, 0)$, where $d > r_A + r_B$.

Initially, both agents select their preferred velocities pointing directly toward their goals: $\mathbf{v}_A^{\text{pref}} = (v_A^{\text{max}}, 0)$ and $\mathbf{v}_B^{\text{pref}} = (-v_B^{\text{max}}, 0)$, resulting in a head-on collision course. Their maximum speeds are constrained so that the relative displacement over a single simulation time step remains smaller than their combined radius scaled by the time-horizon:

$$\Delta t (v_A^{\text{max}} + v_B^{\text{max}}) < \frac{r_A + r_B}{\tau} \quad (1)$$

where Δt is the simulation time step and τ is the ORCA time horizon (the collision-free time window).

2) *ORCA Construction*: The velocity obstacle $\text{VO}_{A|B}^\tau$ induced by agent B on agent A is a truncated cone in VS. The cone has its apex at the origin, with legs tangent to a circle of radius $r_A + r_B$ centered at $\mathbf{p}_B - \mathbf{p}_A$. The truncation arc is a circular segment of radius $(r_A + r_B)/\tau$ centered at $(\mathbf{p}_B - \mathbf{p}_A)/\tau$.

For clarity and concision, the accompanying figures overlay the VS onto the configuration space (agent position), with the VS origin at \mathbf{p}_A .

In this scenario, the preferred velocities of the agents are aligned and opposite. When the agents are sufficiently far apart, their actual velocities initially match their preferred velocities. The relative velocity $\mathbf{v}_A - \mathbf{v}_B$ therefore points from agent A directly toward agent B .

Since the center of the truncation arc lies on the same line, the relative velocity intersects it perpendicularly. Provided the reciprocal velocity vector does not extend beyond the center of the truncation arc ($|\mathbf{v}_A - \mathbf{v}_B| < |\mathbf{p}_B - \mathbf{p}_A|/\tau$), the resulting ORCA line $\text{ORCA}_{A|B}^\tau$ will be orthogonal to the reciprocal velocity.

3) *Velocity Convergence to Zero*: Once the agents are close enough for \mathbf{v}^{pref} to intersect $\text{ORCA}_{A|B}^\tau$, the LP will compute the new velocity \mathbf{v}^{new} by projecting \mathbf{v}^{pref} on $\text{ORCA}_{A|B}^\tau$, resulting in a vector with the same direction and a reduced magnitude.

Consequently, on each subsequent time step, both agents have their speeds reduced proportionally while maintaining their head-on trajectory. The velocity magnitudes decrease monotonically toward zero. Fig. 1 illustrates this convergence: the velocity vectors shorten without changing direction over successive iterations.

As the agents approach each other, the VO cone widens. In the limit where agents become tangent ($|\mathbf{p}_B - \mathbf{p}_A| \rightarrow r_A + r_B$),

Fig. 1: Two agents on a head-on collision course with $\tau = 1.5$. $VO_{A|B}^\tau$ and $ORCA_{A|B}^\tau$ remain orthogonal to the direction of motion throughout convergence, causing monotonic speed reduction without lateral deviation.

the cone degenerates to a half-plane perpendicular to the line connecting the agents. In this configuration, only velocities orthogonal to or opposing the preferred direction remain permitted, preferred velocities are projected into zero vectors and both agents remain indefinitely stationary (deadlock).

This issue stems from exact velocity alignment. Even small deviations amplify over successive iterations, explaining why environmental noise (measurement, actuation) in real-world applications typically prevents this deadlock.

However, in deterministic simulations such as games, these situations occur naturally, especially in urban settings or interiors where straight walls are commonplace. Incidentally, the RVO2 library's circle example [9] escapes this pitfall because the floating-point imprecision in its setup breaks the alignment.

B. Three-Agent Circular Deadlock

1) *Configuration*: A more prevalent deadlock occurs with three agents sharing the same speed configuration, arranged symmetrically. Consider agents A, B, C positioned at angles $0, \frac{2\pi}{3},$ and $-\frac{2\pi}{3}$ on a circle of radius d (with d greater than the sum of any two agent's radius), forming an equilateral triangle with goals at their respective antipodal positions on the circle. Each agent's initial \mathbf{v}^{pref} points toward the circle's center, creating a C3 (three-fold rotational) symmetric collision course.

2) *ORCA Construction*: Each agent has to avoid the two other agents simultaneously, each generating its own VO and its own corresponding ORCA line.

For agent A , agents B and C generate $VO_{A|B}^\tau$ and $VO_{A|C}^\tau$ with the corresponding ORCA lines $ORCA_{A|B}^\tau$ and $ORCA_{A|C}^\tau$, respectively.

These ORCA constraints form two half-planes that intersect to create a reflex wedge of forbidden velocities directly ahead of agent A (see Fig. 2a). $\mathbf{v}_A^{\text{pref}}$ points directly towards the intersection of the two half-planes.

Fig. 2: Three-agent wedge deadlock ($\tau = 1.5$). (a) Reflex wedge formed by dual ORCA constraints on agent A . (b) Velocity magnitude decreases to zero despite changing preferred directions. (c) Collective drift: agents move together as locked group with non-zero velocity.

Specifically, in this case, since the agents start on a circle and converge at the same speed towards its center, their movement is radial, so that their relative velocities point directly towards the corresponding agent. As a result, similarly to the two-agent case, the resulting ORCA-lines will be orthogonal to the relative velocities.

For agent A , the ORCA line induced by agent B , $ORCA_{A|B}^\tau$, has a direction of $\frac{\pi}{3}$, and the ORCA line induced by agent C , $ORCA_{A|C}^\tau$, has a direction of $-\frac{\pi}{3}$, partitioning the VS in four sectors corresponding to the following angular intervals:

- I: $(\frac{\pi}{3}, \frac{2\pi}{3}]$: velocities forbidden by $ORCA_{A|B}^\tau$.
- II: $(\frac{2\pi}{3}, \pi] \cup [-\pi, -\frac{2\pi}{3})$: velocities forbidden by both $ORCA_{A|B}^\tau$ and $ORCA_{A|C}^\tau$.
- III: $[-\frac{2\pi}{3}, -\frac{\pi}{3})$: velocities forbidden by $ORCA_{A|C}^\tau$.
- IV: $[-\frac{\pi}{3}, \frac{\pi}{3}]$: permitted velocities.

3) *Velocity Trapping Mechanism:* Unlike the two-agent case where a single ORCA line blocks progress, and even very small deviations cause the velocities to rapidly diverge, breaking out of the deadlock, here, the two ORCA lines create a concave trap formed of the sectors I, II, and III.

For this symmetric configuration, in all cases where the agent’s $\mathbf{v}_A^{\text{pref}}$ violates both ORCA constraints simultaneously (sector II), the resulting new velocity $\mathbf{v}_A^{\text{new}}$ will be the same: the LP solution $\mathbf{v}_A^{\text{new}}$ is uniquely determined as the intersection of the two ORCA half-plane boundaries in VS, independently of $\mathbf{v}_A^{\text{pref}}$.

This implies that small variations in the agent’s $\mathbf{v}_A^{\text{pref}}$ will not affect the outcome once it violates both ORCA constraints (see Fig. 2b).

4) *Generalization:* This wedge formation generalizes beyond the symmetric circle scenario. Any configuration where three agents’ trajectories converge toward a common point at the same time creates similar constraints. The resulting behaviors range from complete deadlock (stationary agents) to collective drift (agents moving together as a locked group, despite different preferred velocities, see Fig. 2c).

The three-agent deadlock is more common, more stable, and more persistent than the two-agent case in more organic navigation context¹ with homogeneous agent speeds because:

- 1) A relatively wide range of initial conditions lead to the formation of such a wedge and exhibit degenerate outcomes, so that its occurrence does not depend on particularly unfavourable or exceptional circumstances.
- 2) The wedge formed by the constraints guides the new velocity towards its apex, making this situation robust to small perturbations once it has been established.
- 3) Once the agents reach a degenerate state, only backward-facing velocities (sector IV in the enumeration above) remain permitted, making it difficult to recover.

C. Generalization to N-Agent Configurations

1) *Systematic Deadlock:* The two-agent and three-agent deadlocks generalize to arbitrary n agents arranged symmetrically on a circle, each aiming for its antipodal position. When symmetry is preserved, deadlocks occur systematically across all tested values of $n \in [2, 30]$ for agents with preferred speed $v^{\text{max}} = 5$ and time step $\Delta t = 0.25$ (Fig. 3).

The experimental section of the original ORCA article [1] presents this configuration with $n = 2$ and $n = 5$ as successful benchmarks because the reference RVO2 implementation [9] uses single-precision floating-point trigonometric evaluations which introduce small numerical inaccuracies breaking rotational symmetry. Our experiments preserve symmetry explicitly to isolate the geometric properties of ORCA constraints and ensure reproducibility consistently with their mathematical formulation as it occurs in deterministic simulation.

¹Open spaces, natural terrain, as opposed to structured urban environment with long straight obstacles where 2-agent head-on collisions are more likely.

Fig. 3: Various symmetric configurations for n agents (radius $r = 1.5$, $v^{\text{max}} = 5$, $\tau = 1.5$) converging to deadlock at the circle center.

2) *Geometric Mechanism and Sensitivity to Speed and Update Frequency:* The geometric mechanism mirrors the three-agent case: each agent is constrained principally by its two immediate neighbors on the circle (Fig. 3a). As agents converge radially toward the center at equal speeds, their relative velocities remain parallel to the circle’s tangent. The resulting ORCA lines are perpendicular to these tangents, forming a reflex wedge with interior angle $2\pi - 2\pi/n$ and leaving an acute permitted sector of angle $2\pi/n$ bisected by the radial direction.

This geometry guarantees speed reduction without directional change, maintaining perfect radial symmetry. The same configuration repeats at each time step with proportionally reduced distances and speeds until agents contact their neighbors and halt in deadlock.

Empirically, symmetric configurations break when agents use sufficiently high speeds or the simulation uses larger time steps, as floating-point errors grow with velocity magnitude and are amplified by Δt in position updates. This creates a counter-intuitive sensitivity: smaller time steps and slower agents maintain deadlock configurations more reliably.

This is particularly problematic in game contexts. Asynchronous game engines typically reduce time steps when hardware performance allows, meaning implementations may deadlock only on powerful hardware. Moreover, while maximum speeds are controlled by gameplay variables, low speeds emerge naturally in constrained situations (crowded environments, movement through water, crawling, physics constraints, acceleration limits). These observations motivate a deterministic resolution mechanism that does not rely on numerical noise.

IV. REVISED ORCA LOGIC (RORCAL)

The analysis in Section III focused on symmetric configurations to demonstrate the geometric mechanism clearly. However, degenerate solutions can arise in various scenarios beyond perfect symmetry. RORCAL addresses this broader class of configurations.

The VO cut-off circle at radius $(r_A + r_B)/\tau$ permits speed reduction as a geometrically valid avoidance response. This is sometimes desirable, particularly in densely packed scenarios where stopping temporarily can be the only solution. However, the geometric analysis demonstrates that, in symmetric configurations, speed reduction without lateral deviation is often a degenerate solution, leading to deadlock.

Removing the truncation entirely, as in Constant Speed ORCA [10], forces lateral deviation but prevents speed reduction as a solution where it is desirable (constrained environment), and prevents agents from approaching each other directly, which is unacceptable in game context. Adaptive truncation schemes prove unstable, introducing oscillations as constraint geometry changes.

RORCAL is founded on the insight that reducing speed without changing direction is rarely the desired collision-avoidance response. Either \mathbf{v}^{pref} is collision-free and should not be reduced, or collision is imminent and adjusting direction in addition to the speed is more robust. The main exception occurs in densely packed conditions where lateral deviation is geometrically infeasible.

This insight draws loose inspiration from human crowd navigation. Pedestrians coordinate avoidance through subtle non-verbal cues before motion occurs [15]–[17]. RORCAL applies this intuition geometrically by introducing minimal directional bias as a tie-breaker when the LP produces solutions that may lead to deadlock.

A. Detection of Degenerate Solutions

RORCAL operates after ORCA’s LP computes a valid candidate velocity. Correction is attempted when the solution \mathbf{v}^{new} exhibits three characteristics:

- 1) It is constrained (below \mathbf{v}^{pref} magnitude).
- 2) It does not accelerate from the current velocity.
- 3) It maintains the same direction as the current velocity.

These conditions identify the monotonic speed reduction without directional change pattern demonstrated in Section III, whilst avoiding interference with legitimate behaviors such as goal approach or natural obstacle avoidance.

In practice, these conditions are evaluated with small numerical tolerances in the implementation to account for floating-point imprecision, discretization effects, ambient noise, and potentially simulating human perceptual limitations.

B. Directional Bias Correction

When a potentially degenerate solution is detected, RORCAL introduces a small directional deviation. The candidate velocity is rotated by a bias angle α , and the maximum magnitude along this biased direction that satisfies all ORCA

constraints is computed through geometric projection onto the constraint boundaries.

The biased solution is accepted if its magnitude remains sufficiently large relative to the original LP solution. If the first bias direction produces an excessively reduced velocity, the opposite direction is tested. If both directions fail, the original solution is retained as legitimately constrained by the geometry.

The bias angle α should remain small (e.g.: $\simeq 5^\circ$), and represents a trade-off: larger angles ($\simeq 10^\circ$) produce more decisive symmetry breaking but risk severe magnitude reduction in tightly constrained scenarios, whilst smaller angles ($\simeq 1^\circ$) preserve more velocity magnitude but require more iterations to accumulate sufficient deviation. The acceptance threshold is primarily used to reject solutions with a near 0 amplitude, and similarly balances between accepting useful corrections and rejecting geometrically unfavourable deviations.

The initial bias direction is chosen deterministically and maintained consistently across all agents to promote coordinated avoidance behavior. Studies suggest it is strongly influenced by cultural context [18].

C. Persisting Deviation Attempts

An agent may temporarily be unable to deviate laterally while remaining collision-free, though deviation may become possible later. Rather than maintaining explicit temporal state, we extend the deviation condition to speed reduction or conservation $|\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}}| \leq |\mathbf{v}|$ when the speed is constrained. This ensures agents constrained to reduced speed $|\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}}| < v^{\text{max}}$ actively seek alternative collision-free directions whenever available, rather than persisting in suboptimal configurations.

V. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

A. Experimental Setup

We evaluate RORCAL using a modified version of the RVO2 library [9]. Our implementation extends the standard ORCA velocity selection with the bias correction mechanism described in Section IV, whilst preserving all other aspects of the original algorithm.

All experiments use the symmetric circle benchmark configuration: n agents positioned equidistantly on a circle of radius d , each with goal at the antipodal position. Agent radius is set to $r = 1.5$ units, time horizon $\tau = 1.5$ seconds, and maximum speed $v^{\text{max}} = 5.0$ units/second. Time step is $\Delta t = 0.25$ seconds.

As per Section III-C, we preserve exact rotational symmetry in the initial agent placement by sign inversion and coordinate permutation.

We test systematic variations with $n \in [2, 30]$ agents to establish comprehensive coverage of symmetric deadlock scenarios, and $n = 250$ to evaluate performance at scale. For each configuration, we measure the number of iterations required for all agents to reach their goals. An agent is considered to have reached its goal when the distance to the goal is less than the agent’s radius, i.e., $|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{g}_i| \leq r_i$.

Algorithm 1: RORCAL Velocity Selection

Input: Preferred Velocity \mathbf{v}^{pref} , ORCA constraints \mathcal{L}

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1  $\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}} \leftarrow \text{SolveORCA}(\mathcal{L}, \mathbf{v}^{\text{pref}})$ 
2 if solution invalid or infeasible then
3   return FallbackSolver(...) // Standard ORCA
4 if ( $|\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}}| < |\mathbf{v}^{\text{pref}}|$ ) and // constrained
5 ( $|\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}}| \leq |\mathbf{v}|$ ) and // not accelerating
6 ( $\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}} \parallel \mathbf{v}$ ) then // collinear
7    $\mathbf{v}^{\text{rotated}} \leftarrow \text{Rotate}(\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}}, \alpha)$ 
8    $\mathbf{v}^{\text{biased}} \leftarrow \text{ClippedByConstraints}(\mathbf{v}^{\text{rotated}})$ 
9   if  $|\mathbf{v}^{\text{biased}}| \gg 0$  then
10    return  $\mathbf{v}^{\text{biased}}$ 
11  else // Primary deviation failed
12     $\mathbf{v}^{\text{rotated}} \leftarrow \text{Rotate}(\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}}, -\alpha)$ 
13     $\mathbf{v}^{\text{biased}} \leftarrow \text{ClippedByConstraints}(\mathbf{v}^{\text{rotated}})$ 
14    if  $|\mathbf{v}^{\text{biased}}| \gg 0$  then return  $\mathbf{v}^{\text{biased}}$ 
15    else return  $\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}}$ 
16 else
17 return  $\mathbf{v}^{\text{new}}$ 

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$\text{SolveORCA}(\mathcal{L}, \mathbf{v}^{\text{pref}})$ Original ORCA solver (LP2 in RVO2)
 $\text{FallbackSolver}(\dots)$ Original ORCA fallback solver (LP3 in RVO2)
 $\text{ClippedByConstraints}(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{L})$ projects \mathbf{v} onto the feasible interval defined by ORCA lines by computing the admissible parameter range $[t_{\min}, t_{\max}]$ through half-plane intersection, returning $\mathbf{0}$ if infeasible.

RORCAL parameters are set to: detection angle threshold $\theta = \pm\pi/36$, bias angle $\alpha = \pi/20$ (except where noted), and acceptance threshold 10% of the maximum speed v^{max} .

B. Results

1) *Symmetric Deadlock Resolution:* In all 29 symmetric configurations ($n \in [2, 30]$) where ORCA produces deadlock, RORCAL successfully resolves the scenario in a number of iterations shown in Fig. 4.

The iteration count exhibits structured growth from $n = 2$ to $n = 12$, approximately quadratic, indicating predictable non-chaotic behavior. In this regime, agents converge toward the circle center, initiate coordinated counter-clockwise (CCW) rotation following the primary bias direction, and ultimately diverge radially toward their goals once appropriately oriented (Fig. 5c). This emergent rotational flow arises from the consistent directional bias applied across all agents.

From $n = 13$, the symmetry starts breaking during the rotational phase (Fig. 5d) or before rotation begins, resulting in more variable but often shorter completion times.

2) *Performance Analysis:* The benchmark with $n = 250$ agents completes with ORCA in 647 iterations in our experimental setup. The same scenario is resolved in 496 iterations using RORCAL, a 23.3% improvement.

Fig. 7 represents the distribution of the normalized progression of the agents defined as $1 - \frac{\text{current distance to goal}}{\text{initial distance to goal}}$ across iterations. It shows that RORCAL agents converge more quickly to a solution, with a substantially tighter interquartile range. Approximately 75% of ORCA agents are still traveling when RORCAL ends, with some having only reached half the distance to their goal.

Fig. 4: Number of iterations required for completing the traversal of the circle using RORCAL for $n \in [2, 30]$ agents ($\alpha = \pi/18$).

Fig. 5: Traces of representative configurations for n agents.

Frame-by-frame analysis shows that the behavior is similar across both methods for the initial phase where agents converge towards the center, but starts diverging significantly as the agents start constraining each other. In ORCA, the agents converge radially towards the center (Fig. 6a), while in RORCAL, while the agents closest to the center behave similarly, the agents closer to the outside of the cluster initiate a CCW circular movement: as agents in front of them get blocked or slowed, the deviation mechanism encourages them to attempt directional change where possible instead of queuing.

This circular movement of the outside ring of agents evolves in a double spiral which unwinds tangentially to free the agents in the center (see Fig. 6d). Conversely, with ORCA, the outside agents are more likely to attempt to progress radially towards the center, trapping other agents in tight clusters (see Fig. 6c). Once formed, these clusters can remain stable for many iterations, sometimes pulling agents trapped inside the cluster away from their destination. Fig. 6e shows that, with ORCA, some agents are still clustered together after 428 iterations. On the same iteration, some RORCAL agents have reached their destination and all agents have traversed

at least $3/4$ of the distance from their starting point to their destination, leaving the center of the circle clear.

Fig. 6: Comparison of ORCA vs RORCAL for $n = 250$ agents

3) *Computational Overhead*: From a computational standpoint, after the standard ORCA LP is solved, RORCAL performs at most two additional passes over the already constructed ORCA constraint lines. Consequently, the asymptotic per-agent complexity remains identical to ORCA, i.e., linear in the number of considered neighbors.

We evaluate the computational overhead of RORCAL against ORCA on the $n = 250$ circle configuration. Rendering was disabled and each configuration was run 50 times.

	RORCAL (ms)	ORCA (ms)
Total time (ms)	178.30 ± 9.53	227.86 ± 11.11
Time per iteration (ms)	0.359 ± 0.019	0.352 ± 0.017

TABLE I: Comparison of overall runtime and per-iteration cost for $n = 250$ agents. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation.

RORCAL reduces the overall traversal time by approximately 21.8%, primarily due to a reduction in the number of iterations required to resolve the configuration.

When normalized per iteration, RORCAL introduces an average overhead of approximately 2% compared to ORCA. This indicates that the additional adjustment passes incur in average a minimal per-step cost, while enabling significantly faster convergence at system level.

(a) RORCAL: resolves in 496 iterations

(b) ORCA: static cluster, resolves in 647 iterations

Fig. 7: Normalized agent progression toward the goal for $n = 250$ agents. The box-and-whisker plot follows the Tukey convention: the dot indicates the median, the box extents indicate the 25th and 75th percentiles, while whiskers extend to $1.5 \times$ Interquartile Range (IQR).

C. Discussion

RORCAL addresses geometric deadlocks arising from symmetric agent configurations through minimal post-processing of ORCA's LP output. Our results demonstrate that this lightweight intervention resolves all tested symmetric scenarios whilst improving performance in dense crowd scenarios by up to 23%.

The correction mechanism activates selectively: in symmetric configurations, bias is applied consistently, generating emergent coordinated behavior such as the rotational flow observed in the $n = 250$ benchmark. In this highly constrained scenario, the additional passes introduce an average overhead of approximately 2% per iteration, making RORCAL practical for real-time applications.

In typical asymmetric navigation scenarios, the detection criteria triggers less frequently, maintaining ORCA's standard behavior.

The approach has limitations. RORCAL targets velocity-level deadlocks in moderately constrained spaces. Congestion in narrow corridors with bidirectional flow, where agents physically cannot pass, requires higher-level coordination beyond local velocity adjustment. Integration with path planning approaches [2], [3] could address such scenarios. As ROR-

CAL is implemented as a minimal alteration of ORCA, such adjustments should be straightforward to implement.

The parameter sensitivity observed in Section V-B1, where iteration counts vary significantly for $n \geq 13$, reflects RORCAL's interaction with numerical precision and emergent symmetry breaking.

For game development, RORCAL provides deterministic deadlock resolution without relying on numerical noise or explicit randomization. This is particularly valuable for symmetric spawn scenarios, structured environments, and high-fidelity simulation where floating-point variance is minimized.

In ORCA, small time steps or slow agents favor velocity changes over directional changes, which can lead to deadlocks. By introducing a controlled directional bias, RORCAL prevents such persistent symmetry even under fine temporal discretization, mitigating the sensitivity to time step resolution and agent speed.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper identifies and analyzes the geometric causes of deadlock with ORCA for symmetric multiagent configurations often met in deterministic simulations. Through analysis of two-agent and three-agent scenarios generalized to n -agent scenarios, we demonstrate that perpendicular ORCA constraints and reflex constraint wedges produce degenerate LP solutions that reduce agent speed without lateral deviation, leading to monotonic convergence to zero velocity.

We present RORCAL, a lightweight post-processing mechanism that introduces minimal directional bias when degenerate solutions are detected. RORCAL preserves ORCA's computational efficiency and decentralized operation whilst resolving all tested symmetric deadlock scenarios. In the $n = 250$ benchmark, RORCAL achieves resolution in 23% less iterations through emergent rotational coordination, with only 2% per-iteration overhead.

The approach demonstrates that geometric deadlocks in ORCA can be addressed through targeted intervention at velocity selection stage, without modifying the underlying VO construction or constraint formulation. This maintains compatibility with existing ORCA implementations whilst providing robust deadlock resolution for deterministic simulations.

Future work should explore adaptive bias angle selection based on local constraint geometry, integration with global path planning for highly constrained environments, and theoretical analysis of convergence guarantees under RORCAL correction. Extension to heterogeneous agent dynamics and non-circular symmetric configurations would broaden the applicability of the approach.

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